

Community Guidelines

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MetaDocencia Participants Community Guidelines

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Reference Documentation:

- *Some sections of this document were inspired by the Open Life Science [Code of Conduct](#).*

Contact

To communicate with the Community Guidelines team: fdc@metadocencia.org

Foundation and Commitments

We, the contributors of MetaDocencia, are committed to fostering an open, safe, and friendly environment and ensuring the participation of everyone in our activities and virtual spaces, regardless of age, gender, sexual orientation, disability, physical appearance, nationality, ethnicity, beliefs, ideology, or access to resources.

All individuals participating in MetaDocencia, including team members, advisory board members, and participants, must accept and adhere to the following community guidelines.

If you witness a situation where these community guidelines are not being respected, please report it to fdc@metadocencia.org. You may also individually contact any member of the [Community Guidelines team \(CG\)](#).

We encourage the community to embrace and participate in these guidelines, so they represent everyone. We are committed to building a friendly and respectful community, and while we may sometimes fail, our goal is for everyone to be treated fairly, inclusively, and as equitably as possible. We believe that when

someone feels hurt or offended, it is the responsibility of the person who caused those feelings to apologize for the impact of their actions and to listen attentively and respectfully.

To report a problem involving a member of the CG team, send an email to direccion@metadocencia.org. The emails that arrive at this address will be received by the co-directive people of MetaDocencia.

Examples of behavior that contribute to creating a positive environment for our community

- Demonstrating empathy and kindness towards others.
- Respecting different opinions, viewpoints, and experiences.
- Giving and accepting constructive feedback appropriately.
- Taking responsibility and apologizing to those affected by our mistakes, whether intentional or not, and learning from the experience.
- Focusing on what is best not only for ourselves as individuals, but for the community as a whole.
- Correctly identifying ourselves with our personal information when participating synchronously in events or meetings within the MetaDocencia domain.
- Trying to understand why we disagree: disagreements, both social and technical, occur all the time. It is important that we resolve disagreements and divergent opinions constructively. Remember that we are different. Diversity contributes to the strength of our community, which is made up of people from a wide range of backgrounds.

Examples of unacceptable behavior

- Using sexualised language or imagery, as well as unwelcome sexual attention or advances.
- Derogatory comments (trolling), insults, and personal attacks.
- Any form of harassment, whether in public or private

- Posting private information about others, such as physical or email addresses, without their explicit permission.
- Other conduct that could reasonably be considered inappropriate in a community setting
- Any form of mistreatment or disrespect, including ignoring, shaming, marginalizing, denigrating, censoring, etc.

Scope

These Community Guidelines apply to all spaces related to MetaDocencia. This includes our virtual and in-person workshops, our email accounts, our Slack, our social media, our organization on GitHub and all its repositories, and any other channel that is part of MetaDocencia.

Responsibilities of the Community Guidelines Team

The Community Guidelines Team, composed by members of MetaDocencia, is responsible for clarifying the standards of acceptable behavior and reserves the right of admission or permanence, temporary or permanent, in the MetaDocencia community for any behavior deemed unacceptable.

The team also has the responsibility and reserves the right to remove, edit, or reject comments, materials, and other contributions that do not align with these community guidelines.

Reports of unacceptable behavior can be made by sending an email to pdcc@metadocencia.org or contacting any member of the Community Guidelines Team. All messages will be reviewed, followed up on, and will result in an appropriate response to the circumstances. The confidentiality of the affected individuals will always be respected, and care will be provided to those who contact the Community Guidelines Team to report an incident. The [Community Guidelines Intervention Protocol](#) serves as a framework and establishes both a working guide for the team and principles for acting in situations that require intervention.

Members of the Community Guidelines Team commit to recusing themselves if they have a conflict of interest related to handling a case, in accordance with [MetaDocencia's Conflict of Interest](#) policy.

These Community Guidelines are subject to continuous review.

About the Development of this Document

This document was generated within the framework of the Open Seeds 8 program by OLS.

This publication was made possible thanks to a grant from NASA 80NSSC23K0854 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8215455](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8215455) and grant DAF2021-239366 from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative DAF (Grant DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37921/522107izqogv>).

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This is the quote that we recommend you use to reference it: Laura Ascenzi, Paola Lefer, Romina Pendino, Iván Poggio, Verónica Xhárdez (2024). "MetaDocencia Community Guidelines 2024". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13236269>